

MODELING APPROACH FOR THE HIGH PRESSURE SOLID-FLUID EQUILIBRIUM OF ASYMMETRIC SYSTEMS

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In this work, we evaluate the potential of a modeling approach for describing the solid-fluid equilibria of highly asymmetric mixtures over a wide pressure range. The model uses a mathematical expression for the fugacity of a pure heavy compound in solid state for which the reference state is the saturated solid under conditions of solid-liquid (melting) equilibrium at the system temperature T . Such reference state differs from a common choice which corresponds to the pure solid under conditions of solid-vapor (sublimation) equilibrium at T . By construction, the present modeling approach matches the solid-liquid equilibria at high concentration of the heavy component. We discuss and test here a parameterization strategy for avoiding the simultaneous correlation of fluid-fluid and solid-fluid experimental data: first the fluid-fluid equilibrium experimental data are correlated in the conventional way, and, next, the solid-fluid equilibrium data are correlated by fitting a parameter that has no influence on the equation of state that describes the fluid phases. In this work, we study in detail the highly asymmetric system methane + n-triacontane, for which experimental data are available over a wide range of conditions¹. To model this system we use a specific form of the present modeling approach. Such specific model gives a good quantitative performance even at pressures in the order of 2000 bar. Besides, we present additional modeling results for two other systems, i.e., for methane + n-eicosane and methane + n-tetracosane, which are also highly asymmetric.

Keywords: Solid-Fluid equilibria, Fluid Phase equilibria, Modeling approach, Binary n-alkane systems, High pressure

INTRODUCTION

The accurate description of the fluid-fluid and solid-fluid (SF) equilibria of multicomponent

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asymmetric mixtures, over wide ranges of conditions, is a problem of industrial and scientific interest. The corresponding models should be able, as a necessary condition, to reproduce the experimental behavior of binary asymmetric sub-systems. The use of equations of state (EOS) to model the fluid-fluid equilibria of such kind of mixtures is widely extended. EOSs are able to describe the properties of vapors, liquids and supercritical fluids ⁴. Simple EOS models, such as the PR-EOS⁵, are quite consistent. More sophisticated models can have an inconsistent behavior⁶.

For binary asymmetric mixtures, the solubility of the light component in the solid phase is very often assumed to be negligible. Therefore, the modeling of the solid-fluid equilibrium of such mixtures requires defining an expression for the fugacity of the heavy component (component “2” in this work) in pure solid state as a function of temperature (T) and pressure (P). It is also needed to choose an EOS for describing the component fugacities in the (mixed) fluid phase.

When computing solid solubilities in compressed gases, the following expression is conventionally used for describing the fugacity of the pure solid⁷ (component “2”) at given absolute temperature T and absolute pressure P , i.e., f_2^S :

$$f_2^S(T, P) = f_2^{sat,SV}(T) \exp\left\{\frac{v_2^S [P - P_2^{sat,SV}(T)]}{RT}\right\} \quad (1)$$

where

$$f_2^{sat,SV}(T) = P_2^{sat,SV}(T) \varphi_2^{sat,SV}(T) \quad (2)$$

In the previous equations, $f_2^{sat,SV}$, $P_2^{sat,SV}$ and $\varphi_2^{sat,SV}$ are, respectively, the solid-vapor (SV, sublimation) saturation fugacity, saturation pressure and saturation fugacity coefficient, of the pure substance “2” at T ; while v_2^S is the molar volume of the pure solid at T . R is the universal gas constant. $f_2^{sat,SV}$ equals both, the fugacity of the saturated solid and the fugacity of the saturated vapor. Since the sublimation pressure is always low, it is often assumed that the vapor phase is an ideal gas, i.e., $\varphi_2^{sat,SV}$ is set equal to unity. The exponential factor in eq 1, i.e., the Poynting correction, accounts for departure from the SV saturation condition.

Equation 1 has been used to describe SF and solid-fluid-fluid (SFF) equilibrium conditions by several authors^{8, 9, 10, 11, 12}. The sublimation pressure $P_2^{sat,SV}$ at the system temperature has been obtained from experimental data, sometimes using the Antoine equation to interpolate/extrapolate the experimental sublimation data^{8,12,13}. $P_2^{sat,SV}$ has also been approximated by extrapolating liquid-vapor saturation pressure data to low temperatures using the Clausius-Clapeyron equation¹¹. All these authors have used an equation of state (EOS), of the van der Waals type, for the calculation of $\varphi_2^{sat,SV}$ or the Sanchez-Lacombe EOS¹⁵, as in ref⁹. It is also possible to use the virial equation for computing $\varphi_2^{sat,SV}$ ⁷. Neau et al.¹⁴ have proposed an approach for estimating the sublimation pressure $P_2^{sat,SV}$, which uses the experimental normal fusion temperature and fusion enthalpy, and vapor pressure data. In the literature, e.g., in refs^{8, 9} and¹¹, eq 1 has been used to predict solid-fluid equilibrium conditions at temperatures below the triple point temperature of the heavy compound. This is due to the reference state on which eq 1 stands, i.e., the sublimation pressure line. It is also possible to compute the fugacity of a pure solid as follows:

$$f_2^S(T, P) = f_2^{sat,SL}(T) \exp\left\{\frac{v_2^S [P - P_2^{sat,SL}(T)]}{RT}\right\} \quad (3)$$

where

$$f_2^{sat,SL}(T) = P_2^{sat,SL}(T) \varphi_2^{sat,SL}(T) \quad (4)$$

In eqs 3 and 4 the subscript “SL” stands for solid-liquid equilibrium. Thus, the reference state for eq 3 is the saturated substance under conditions of solid-liquid equilibrium. In other words the reference on which eq 3 stands is the pure substance melting line, i.e., the $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ curve. While eq 1 is applicable at temperatures less than the substance triple point temperature (T_{tp}), eq 3 is applicable at temperatures greater than T_{tp} . More generally, eq 3 is applicable at any temperature at which a SL saturation point exists, independently on whether such temperature is less than T_{tp} or greater than T_{tp} .

To our knowledge eq 3 has not been used previously in the literature as part of a model for describing the solid-fluid equilibria (SFE) of highly asymmetric mixtures over a wide pressure range. The purpose of this work is thus to evaluate the potential of a SFE modeling approach based on eq 3. To that end, we define a specific form of the general modeling

approach, choose a specific highly asymmetric system as our detailed case study, and look at the quantitative performance of the model by comparing model calculations and experimental SFE data. Finally, we also study two other highly asymmetric binary systems for which experimental data are available over wide ranges of conditions.

OPTIONS FOR EQUATION 3

For using eq 3, we need to make specifications for $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$, $\phi_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ and v_2^S . The function $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ can be obtained from correlating experimental pure-compound solid-liquid equilibrium data in a wide enough pressure range, if available. Otherwise, $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ can be obtained from integrating, in the conventional way, the Clapeyron equation. This last choice requires having available experimental information on the enthalpy change on melting and on the pure substance molar volume change on melting. Such properties are typically assumed independent from temperature, and next the SL saturation pressure is integrated with respect to temperature. In this work we somehow combine both alternatives, as explained in detail in section “PARAMETERIZATION OF THE MODEL”. If the expression for $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ reproduces the experimental pure compound solid-liquid equilibrium data within the experimental uncertainty, then, eq 3 reproduces the melting pressure at given temperature within experimental uncertainty too. The fugacity coefficient $\phi_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ can be computed from an EOS able to represent all possible fluid states (liquid, vapour and supercritical), e.g., a van der Waals type EOS. Actually, such EOSs make possible to compute pure compound fugacity coefficients after specifying two variables, such as temperature and pressure. The EOS-based calculation of $\phi_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ at given T , is performed by setting the pressure equal to $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$, and by choosing a liquid-like root for the molar volume at conditions where more than a single root exists. Finally the molar volume of the pure solid v_2^S can be available from experimental determinations of molar volumes for pure solids. It could also be obtained from regression of experimental binary SFE data.

THE METHANE (CH₄) + N-TRIACONTANE (N-C₃₀H₆₂) SYSTEM

To assess the potential of the present modeling approach for describing the SFE of complex systems, we have chosen as a representative case study the system methane (CH₄) + n-

triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂). It is highly asymmetric with regard to molecular size. A good deal of experimental fluid-fluid and solid-fluid equilibrium information is available in the literature for this system (Machado and de Loos ¹). The system has a phase behavior of type III ¹⁶ with a metastable liquid-liquid phase split ¹. This type of behavior is characterized by the existence of two branches of the solid + liquid + vapor (SLV) locus. Either branch ends at a critical endpoint where a binary critical fluid phase is at equilibrium with the pure solid heavy n-alkane. The low temperature SLV branch originates at a solid-solid-liquid-vapor quadruple point, and runs to higher temperature until it intersects the vapor-liquid critical curve at the first critical end point (1st CEP). The high temperature branch stems from the triple point of the pure heavy n-alkane and runs to higher pressures until it intersects the vapor-liquid critical curve at the second critical endpoint (2nd CEP). For more details, see reference ¹. To our knowledge, the CH₄ + n-C₃₀H₆₂ experimental data of Machado and de Loos ¹ have not been yet used in the open literature either to test model predictions or to fit model parameters. We also present modeling results for the systems methane + n-eicosane and methane + n-tetracosane.

SOLID-FLUID EQUILIBRIUM CALCULATIONS IN BINARY SYSTEMS

In this work, we adopted the Peng-Robinson (1976) equation of state (PR-EOS) ⁵ for defining, for binary mixtures, the relationship $[P = h_{PVT}(T, z_2, \nu)]$ among the absolute pressure (P), the absolute temperature (T), the molar volume (ν) and the composition ($z_2 =$ mole fraction of component 2, i.e., of the heavy component) for the fluid state (pure fluids or fluid mixtures). From exact thermodynamics, once we define an appropriate pressure-temperature-volume-composition (PVTx) relationship, the expressions for other thermodynamic properties, such as the component fugacities in the mixture \hat{f}_1 and \hat{f}_2 , become defined.

In other words, the functions $h_{PVT}(T, z_2, \nu)$ and $\hat{f}_i(T, z_2, \nu)$ are known functions of variables T , z_2 and ν once a specific EOS, such as the PR-EOS, has been adopted for the fluid state.

In eq 3, $f_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ is the fugacity of the saturated pure substance “2” under solid-liquid equilibrium (SLE) conditions. It equals, in particular, the fugacity of the saturated liquid at SLE. We define ν_o as the volume of such pure saturated liquid. ν_o is calculated at set T ,

from the adopted EOS and from the known $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$ curve by solving the following equation:

$$\ln\left[P_2^{sat,SL}(T)\right] - \ln\left[h_{PVT}(T, 1, \nu_o)\right] = 0 \quad (5)$$

Once ν_o is known, the fugacity of the pure saturated liquid at SLE at T is given by the EOS as $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$, i.e., $f_2^{sat,SL}(T) = \hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$, and next, from eq 3, the fugacity of the pure solid at T and P is obtained as $f_2^S(T, P) = \hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o) \exp\left\{\nu_2^S \left[P - P_2^{sat,SL}(T) \right] / RT\right\}$, as long as ν_2^S is known. Since when we look at such previous expression for $f_2^S(T, P)$ the variables (not parameters) that we actually see are T , P and ν_o , we add ν_o to the list of arguments for f_2^S , i.e.,

$$f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o) = \hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o) \exp\left\{\frac{\nu_2^S}{RT} \left[P - P_2^{sat,SL}(T) \right]\right\} \quad (6)$$

Indeed, ν_o depends on T according to the prescription that eq 5 establishes. It should be borne in mind that in this work we assumed that the solid phase is only made of the pure heavy component “2”. Therefore, we use eq 6 in all SFE calculations in this work. Under solid-liquid equilibrium conditions for the pure compound “2” the solid fugacity $f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o)$ and the liquid fugacity $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$ are equal. By imposing this condition in eq 6, we consistently obtain the identity $P = P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$.

The system of equations we use here for modelling the relationship between temperature T , pressure P , and fluid phase composition y_2 , at conditions of solid-fluid equilibrium, for a binary asymmetric mixture, when assuming the solid phase as made of the pure heavy compound, is made of eq 5 coupled to the following equations :

$$\ln(P) - \ln\left[h_{PVT}(T, y_2, \nu_y)\right] = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\ln\left[f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o)\right] - \ln\left[\hat{f}_2(T, y_2, \nu_y)\right] = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o)$ is defined by eq 6.

The variables y_2 and v_y are, respectively, the composition (i.e., mole fraction of component 2) and molar volume of the fluid mixture at equilibrium with the pure solid “2”. Equation 8 is the isofugacity condition for the heavy component in the fluid and solid phases. Equations 5, 7 and 8 imply that the system pressure P and temperature T are the same for both equilibrium phases. The five variables of the system of eqs 5, 7 and 8 are T , P , v_o , y_2 and v_y . Thus, it is clear that there are two degrees of freedom that must be set to compute a solid-fluid equilibrium point. For solving the system of eqs 5, 7 and 8 we used the full Newton’s method, i.e., the Newton’s method with analytic derivatives.

From eq 6, it is clear that $f_2^S(P, T, v_o)$ depends on $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$. A flexible expression for the solid-fluid saturation pressure [$P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$] of the pure heavy component “2” (e.g., n-C₃₀H₆₂ for our detailed case study methane + n-triacontane) is the following:

$$P_2^{sat,SL}(T) = P_p + C_I \ln\left(\frac{T}{T_p}\right) + C_{II}(T - T_p) + C_{III}(T^2 - T_p^2) \quad (9)$$

In eq 9, T_p is the experimental triple point temperature of the pure heavy compound “2” and C_I , C_{II} and C_{III} are constants that characterize the melting curve of pure compound “2”. P_p is the triple point pressure of compound “2” obtained, for consistency reasons, as the liquid-vapour pure-compound saturation pressure given by the adopted EOS at T_p . We obtained eq 9 by integrating the SLE Clapeyron equation, from $[T_p, P_p]$ to $[T, P_2^{sat,SL}(T)]$, after having assumed a quadratic temperature dependency for the ratio between the SLE enthalpy change on fusion and the SLE volume change on fusion.

To fix ideas, we provide a calculation example in Appendix A. Such example corresponds to the computation of the SF equilibrium at 340.34 K and 583.8 bar for the system methane + n-triacontane.

PARAMETERIZATION OF THE MODEL

Parameters for the SLE of Pure n-Triacontane

We obtained values for the constants C_I , C_{II} and C_{III} of eq 9 from the solid-liquid

equilibrium experimental data available, for pure n-triacontane, in ref ¹. Table 1 reports all parameter values that eq 9 requires, for n-triacontane. Figure 1 shows the quantitative performance of eq 9 for n-triacontane, among other n-alkanes. Within the temperature range of Figure 1, eq 9 gives an always positive slope for pressure as a function of temperature. This implies a positive value, at a given temperature, for the ratio between the SLE enthalpy change on fusion and the SLE molar volume change on fusion. This is so in spite of the negative values for C_I and C_{II} in Table 1.

Parameters for the Fluid-Fluid Equilibrium For Methane + n-Triacontane

Table 3 presents the pure compound critical properties and acentric factors that we used for the compounds of the mixture methane + n-triacontane within the PR-EOS. With the help of the SPECS ¹⁷ software package, we fitted the PR-EOS interaction parameters k_{ij} (attractive) and l_{ij} (repulsive) by reproducing experimental bubble pressure data from ref ¹ for the system CH₄ (1) + n-C₃₀H₆₂ (2). Table 2 reports the optimum k_{ij} and l_{ij} values we found for the system. The AAD% value for the bubble pressure, corresponding to Table 2 interaction parameters, is 5.7 % for the system methane + n-triacontane.

Figure 2 shows the calculated and experimental fluid-fluid equilibrium pressure as a function of temperature at a number of constant n-C₃₀H₆₂ mole fraction values ($x_{n-C30H62}=\text{const.}$), for methane + n-triacontane. Most of the isopleths are bubble pressure curves. The pressure range is wide. The $x_{n-C30H62} = 0.02$ isopleth is a dew point curve. We observe that pressure increases as $x_{n-C30H62}$ decreases from $x_{n-C30H62} = 0.701$ to $x_{n-C30H62} = 0.03$, and that the pressure at $x_{n-C30H62} = 0.02$ is slightly less than the pressure at $x_{n-C30H62} = 0.03$; this behavior corresponds to critical or near critical conditions. In other words, the system methane + n-triacontane, at liquid-vapour (LV) equilibrium conditions, exhibits pressure maxima in the temperature range of Figure 2 when the pressure is plotted as function of mole fraction at constant temperature. From Figure 2, we conclude that the PR-EOS, with the values for the interaction parameters from Table 2, gives an acceptable representation of the LV equilibrium conditions for the system methane + n-triacontane.

The issue of how well equations of state reproduce liquid molar volumes has been extensively discussed in the literature. As long as one is interested in the relationship among pressure,

temperature and phase compositions at equilibrium, the molar volumes of the phases can be regarded just as intermediate variables whose impact is kept, as much as possible, under control, for EOSs such as the PR-EOS, through the fitted interaction parameters, in the case of mixtures, and, for the pure compounds, through the experimental critical temperature, critical pressure and acentric factor (and often also through some additional adjustable pure compound parameter).

Determination of Parameter v_2^s

Once we assign values to k_{ij} and l_{ij} , we are left with only one more parameter value to specify, i.e., the value for parameter v_2^s . From eq 6, if P equals $P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$, then, the solid-liquid isofugacity condition is automatically satisfied for the pure component “2”, regardless the value for v_2^s . Therefore, the pure compound parameter v_2^s has no influence on the calculated pure heavy component melting curve. Thus, we can use v_2^s as a degree of freedom for matching the available experimental solubility data for the binary system. We did so for methane+n-triacontane using the SFE data from ref¹. The optimum value we found for v_2^s is $0.63 \text{ m}^3/\text{Kmol}$ (Table 1). Using a fitted value for v_2^s , instead of the experimental value for the volume of the pure heavy solid, makes possible to counterbalance the inadequacies of the adopted EOS (PR-EOS in this work) and of the effects of the assumption of a pure solid volume independent from T and P .

With regard to the parameterization of the model, it is clear that, in this work, we first deal with the binary fluid-fluid equilibrium and then with the binary solid-fluid equilibrium, i.e., we consider both equilibrium situations in a sequential way. It would also be possible to fit all parameters simultaneously.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We carried out the Solid-Fluid equilibrium (SF) calculations for the system methane (CH₄) + n-triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂) by solving the system of eqs 5, 7 and 8 to construct SF isothermal or isobaric or isoplethic lines.

Figure 3 shows the model description (lines) of the SF equilibrium for CH₄ + n-C₃₀H₆₂ together with raw SFE experimental data (markers) for a number of isoplethic cuts (constant

fluid phase composition) in their pressure-temperature projections. At a given overall composition, i.e., for a given SF isoplethic line, the mixture is in fluid state below the SF isoplethic line, and in solid-fluid state both, on and above the SF isoplethic line. The calculations performed with the model are limited to temperature values greater than or equal to the pure n-C₃₀H₆₂ triple point temperature (vertical dashed line in Figure 3). We observe an acceptable agreement between the experimental data and the model. The performance is better at high n-triacontane concentration. The model becomes less accurate at low n-triacontane concentration, e.g., for the isopleths at $x_{n-C_{30}H_{62}} = 0.020$ to $x_{n-C_{30}H_{62}} = 0.050$. (this can be better seen in Figure 4). However, the model properly captures the arousal of intersection points for the isopleths at lowest n-C₃₀H₆₂ concentration values (Figure 4).

In Figure 3, we also present the solid-liquid-vapour (SLV) equilibrium (full black circles) data from Machado and de Loos¹. Those authors have reported the coordinates of the second critical end point (2nd CEP) of the SLV curve, where pure solid n-C₃₀H₆₂ is at equilibrium with a critical binary fluid phase. The experimental 2nd CEP coordinates are the following: $T = 340.73 \pm 0.4$ K and $P = 1285.5 \pm 5$ bar, and $x_{n-C_{30}H_{62}} = 0.0275 \pm 0.002$ ($x_{n-C_{30}H_{62}} =$ n-C₃₀H₆₂ mole fraction)¹. In this work, we present only a few three-phase equilibrium calculation results because most of the SLV behaviour for the studied system occurs at temperatures below the triple point temperature of n-triacontane, where the present model is not applicable.

Figures 3 and 4 show, at a glance, and through constant composition (isoplethic) cuts, how the SFE model performs. This is complemented by Figure 2 which presents the description of the fluid-fluid equilibria. The direct calculation of isopleths is especially practical for highly asymmetric systems, as the CH₄ + n-C₃₀H₆₂ system, for which experimental data are typically gathered at constant composition¹. We can also visualize the model performance through isothermal or isobaric cuts. However, this implies the need of generating isothermal or isobaric “experimental” data, from smoothing the raw constant composition experimental data of ref¹, through low order polynomial fitting functions. This is the case for the “experimental” data shown in Figures 5, 6, 7, C.1, C.2 and C.3, where we present the performance of the model for both, the fluid-fluid and the solid-fluid equilibria.

Figures 5, 6 and 7 show our LV and SF equilibrium calculation results together with the

experimental data for the system $\text{CH}_4 + \text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ for the isothermal cuts at 340.34 K, at 343.15 K and at 353.15 K respectively. Consistently with Figures 3 and 4, we confirm, in those constant temperature cuts, the good performance for the SF equilibrium model. In contrast with Figures 3 and 4, in Figures 5, 6 and 7 it is possible to see the calculated compositions of all the coexisting equilibrium phases.

At 340.34 K, i.e., in Figure 5, the model gives a three-phase equilibrium point (SLV point) (circles) at 1280.5 bar (horizontal dashed line) which we were able to calculate because the triple point temperature T_p (Table 1) is less than the temperature of this isothermal cut. Three equilibrium regions stem from the SLV point: a solid-vapour region (solid lines) that extends to high pressure, a liquid-vapour region (dashed lines and full black triangles) that ends at the pure n-triacontane vapour-liquid saturation pressure, which is low, and a solid-liquid region (solid line and empty triangles) that extends towards low pressures and ends at the pure n-triacontane solid-liquid saturation pressure. Notice that the vertical line at unity n-triacontane mole fraction starts at the pure n-triacontane solid-liquid equilibrium point. Such vertical line indicates that the solid phase in either of the solid-fluid regions is made of only the pure heavy component. The empty triangles and the associated line represent liquids saturated with respect to a pure solid phase. On the other hand, the full black triangles and the associated dashed line represent liquids saturated with respect to a vapour phase. In between both types of saturated liquids there is a homogenous liquid region. This happens in a pressure range with maximum pressure equal to the SLV pressure.

The isotherm at 340.34 K of Figure 5 has three key points: a pure n-triacontane vapour-liquid equilibrium point at low pressure, a pure n-triacontane solid-liquid equilibrium point at higher pressure, and a SLV equilibrium point at a much higher pressure. These three key points establish the number and nature of the regions in Figure 5 (1 vapour-solid region, 1 liquid-solid region, 1 vapour-liquid region, 1 homogeneous liquid region and 1 homogeneous vapour region which has a relatively small size).

At 343.15 K (Figure 6), the homogenous liquid region is larger than at 340.34 K (Figure 5). This is related to the greater increase, for pure n-triacontane, in the melting pressure with respect to the increase in the vapour pressure when going from 340.34 K to 343.15 K. The PR-EOS, used with parameters from Tables 2 and 3, over predicts the mixture critical pressure at 343.15 K. For the model, the liquid-vapor critical point is very close to the SF

equilibrium line. Thus, such predicted critical point is close to the second critical end point predicted by the model. For the model, the 2nd CEP coordinates are approximately $T = 343.15$ K and $P = 1540$ bar, while the experimental coordinates are $T = 340.73 \pm 0.4$ K and $P = 1285.5 \pm 5$ bar¹. The PR-EOS is a classical EOS, i.e., it does not account for the special behavior that real fluids have in the neighborhood of the critical point.

Figure 7 presents the isotherm at 353.15 K, which has three key points, i.e., the pure n-triacontane melting and vapour pressure points and a binary vapour-liquid critical point. The presence of three key points at 353.15 K could have been anticipated from Figure 8 which shows, on the PT plane, the calculated melting curve for pure n-C₃₀H₆₂ and the calculated vapour pressure curve for pure n-C₃₀H₆₂ together with the calculated binary vapor-liquid critical locus. We calculated the critical locus according to ref¹⁸. We have also included in Figure 8 the experimental solid-liquid-vapor equilibrium data from ref¹. The key points at 353.15 K are seen in Figure 8, as the intersection points of the vertical line at 353.15 K (also shown in Figure 8) with the n-triacontane vapour pressure curve (intersection at very low pressure), with the n-triacontane melting curve and with the critical line. Figure 8 also shows the vertical constant temperature lines corresponding to Figures 5 (340.34 K) and 6 (343.15 K). In Figure 7, the difference between the melting pressure and the vapour-liquid pressure for pure n-triacontane is even greater than for Figures 5 and 6. This is related to the higher size of the homogenous fluid region in Figure 7.

In Appendix B we present additional modeling results for two other highly asymmetric systems, i.e., for methane + n-eicosane and methane + n-tetracosane, for which, according to Appendix B, the model quantitative performance is similar to that obtained for CH₄ + n-C₃₀H₆₂. For this last system (the most asymmetric of the three studied in this work), we further discuss the behavior of the model in Appendix C.

REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have proposed to model the solid-fluid equilibria of highly asymmetric mixtures over a wide pressure range using, as a reference state, the saturated solid under conditions of solid-liquid (melting) equilibrium at the temperature T of the system. This contrasts with the usual reference state that corresponds to the pure solid under conditions of solid-vapor (sublimation) equilibrium. We have considered the situation where the solid

phase is made of only the pure heavy component of a binary system. The “melting” reference state is (generally) applicable at temperatures higher than the pure heavy component triple point temperature (T_{tp}), while the “sublimation” reference state is applicable below T_{tp} . Using the “sublimation” reference at temperatures greater than T_{tp} could result, among other possible problems, in unacceptable fugacity values for the pure heavy component, due to the blind extrapolation of the sublimation curve beyond its natural range of applicability. Such blind extrapolation could produce calculated conditions for pure compound solid-liquid equilibria far from the experimental ones. This might be overcome by using v_2^s in eq 1 as an adjustable parameter, fit to impose a good reproduction of the experimental pure compound solid-liquid equilibrium curve. However, such choice would leave the model without additional parameters to be fit to reproduce mixture solid-fluid equilibrium data. Besides, extrapolating the sublimation curve indeed requires the availability of such curve, which should be based on experimental sublimation data. Due to the extremely low values of the sublimation pressures of pure heavy compounds, the experimental sublimation data might have a high level of uncertainty. Such uncertainty would be inevitably inherited by whatever extrapolation scheme adopted to compute fictitious sublimation pressures at temperatures greater than the triple point temperature. Besides, experimental sublimation data might not be available at all, due to the difficulties associated to the measurement of extremely low pressures. For a heavy pure compound, it may be easier and cheaper to measure a high pressure segment of the solid-liquid equilibrium curve than to measure a (low pressure) segment of the sublimation curve, which, regardless the attained experimental accuracy, would be anyway blindly extrapolated when intending to calculate mixture solid-fluid equilibria at high temperature. On the other hand, the “melting” reference cannot (generally) be used at temperatures less than T_{tp} because, due to its high slope, the pure compound melting curve quickly gives negative pressures, at which it does not make sense to intend to solve eq 5 using the adopted equation of state (EOS).

Since the essential difference between eq 1 (sublimation reference) and eq 3 (melting reference) lies on the choice of the reference state, both approaches do not basically differ in their level of thermodynamic consistency. This consistency, the good (and independent) description of the pure heavy compound solid-liquid experimental data (eq 9) and mixture fluid-fluid data (PR-EOS), and, finally, the use of a suitable (non-experimental) value for the volume of the pure heavy solid (v_2^s), are the reasons to which we ascribe the satisfactory

quantitative performance of eq 3 (or its equivalent eq 6) in describing the solid-fluid equilibria of the highly asymmetric binary systems here studied.

The results of this work correspond to a specific choice for the equation of state (EOS) for describing the properties of the (pure and mixed) fluid phases, i.e., to the PR-EOS, used with interaction parameters not dependent on temperature. Since other, probably better, EOSs could be chosen, i.e., consistent EOSs more flexible with respect to composition and temperature, the results of the present work should be seen as a mean for evaluating the potential of a modeling approach rather than just as the results for a particular model. Our conclusion is that the present approach has a good potential for the quantitative description, at high enough temperature, of the solid-fluid equilibria of highly asymmetric mixtures. The results in this work should, at least, be useful to interpolate experimental SFE data and/or to estimate, through extrapolation, the system behavior at pressure conditions beyond those of the available data, thus guiding the definition of conditions for conducting new experimental determinations.

If we chose an EOS applicable to multicomponent systems, such as the PR-EOS, then, we can use the present modeling approach for multicomponent systems, at high enough temperature, as long as it is acceptable to assume that all solid phases present at equilibrium are made of pure compounds.

With regard to the parameterization of the model, we first fitted the EOS interaction parameters using only fluid-fluid equilibrium data. Next, we used the volume of the pure heavy compound (v_2^s) as a degree of freedom to match solid-fluid equilibrium data. We did so having previously represented the pure heavy compound solid-fluid equilibrium curve using a suitable mathematical expression (eq 9). In the absence of experimental information on the melting curve of the pure precipitating component (and of a reliable way of estimating such melting curve), both v_2^s and the slope of the melting curve could be fit simultaneously, against solid-fluid equilibrium data for the binary mixture. We stress that the value for v_2^s is unique (Table 1) for all the modeling results presented in this work for the system methane + n-triacontane. The situation is the same for the systems of Appendix B. It would also be possible to fit the EOS interaction parameters and the v_2^s parameter simultaneously, using to that end experimental fluid-fluid and solid-fluid equilibrium data together.

A potential approach to be explored, with the aim of improving the representation of critical end points (CEPs), where a critical fluid phase is at equilibrium with a pure solid, is to choose an EOS, for the fluid phases, accounting for the special behavior that real fluids have under near-critical conditions (cross-over EOSs).

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APPENDIX A: CALCULATION EXAMPLE: Computation of fluid phase composition and molar volume for the system methane + n-triacontane under conditions of solid-fluid equilibrium at $T = 340.34$ K and $P = 583.8$ bar.

- Compute the solid-liquid saturation pressure [$P_2^{sat,SL}(T)$] for pure n-triacontane at $T = 340.34$ K from eq 9, using the constants C_I , C_{II} and C_{III} , and the triple point temperature T_{tp} and pressure P_{tp} from Table 1. The result is $P_2^{sat,SL}(340.36) = 66.64$ bar, which is much less than the system pressure.
- Solve eq 5 for the volume (ν_o) of pure n-triacontane in liquid state (saturated, at equilibrium with pure solid n-triacontane). The result is $\nu_o = 0.71505$ $m^3/Kmol$. The parameter values used in the second term of the left hand side of eq 5 (PR-EOS) are those for pure n-triacontane in Table 3.
- Compute the pure liquid n-triacontane fugacity $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$ using the PR-EOS. This is the fugacity of pure liquid n-triacontane at equilibrium with pure solid n-triacontane at 340.34 K (and indeed at 66.64 bar). The parameter values here required are those for pure n-triacontane in Table 3. The result is $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o) = 1.57619 \cdot 10^{-3}$ bar.
- Calculate the fugacity of pure solid n-triacontane $f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o)$ at $T = 340.34$ K and $P = 583.8$ bar from eq 6, using the value given in Table 1 for the pure n-triacontane solid volume ν_2^s ($\nu_2^s = 0.6300$ $m^3/Kmol$). The result is $f_2^S(P, T, \nu_o) = 1.57503 \cdot 10^{-8}$ bar.

- Solve the set of equations 7 and 8 for y_2 and v_y using the interaction parameters of Table 2 and the pure compound parameters of Table 3. The result is $y_2 = 0.3344$ and $v_y = 3.7951 \text{ m}^3/\text{Kmol}$.

In the previous calculation procedure the system of equations 5, 7 and 8 was split into a couple of subsystems: the single nonlinear eq 5 on one hand, and the set of equations 7 and 8, on the other. This is suitable if we specify temperature and pressure, but not for other specifications such as temperature and fluid phase composition. Thus, actually, in this work, we have always solved eqs 5, 7 and 8 simultaneously, irrespective of the chosen specification for the two degrees of freedom of the system.

APPENDIX B: MODELING RESULTS FOR THE SYSTEMS METHANE + N-EICOSANE AND METHANE + N-TETRACOSANE

In this section we present the modeling results we obtained for two additional tested systems: methane + n-eicosane and methane + n-tetracosane. The model and parameterization procedure are the same as that used for the methane + n-triacontane system. Table B.1 provides the values the pure compound constants for n-C₂₀H₄₂ and n-C₂₄H₅₀ (T_p , P_p , C_I , C_{II} , C_{III} and v_2^s). Table B.2 reports the optimum k_{ij} and l_{ij} values we found for each system, the AAD% value for the bubble pressure and the corresponding experimental data source. Finally, Table B.3 shows the critical parameters and acentric factors for n-C₂₀H₄₂ and n-C₂₄H₅₀. For pure methane, the critical parameters and acentric factor are again those of Table 3.

In Figure 1 of the main body of this article, the quantitative performance of eq 9 for n-eicosane and n-tetracosane is shown. We observe a positive slope for the calculated melting curve of either compound in the temperature range of Figure 1. We obtained the constants C_I , C_{II} and C_{III} from the pure compound solid-liquid equilibrium experimental data available for each system (refs ² and ³ respectively). These experimental data are also shown in Figure 1.

Figure B.1 presents the model description (lines) of the SF equilibrium for CH₄ + n-C₂₀H₄₂ together with the raw experimental data (markers) for a number of isoplethic cuts. Moreover the experimental coordinates of the SLV equilibrium point are also shown (full black circles).

In Figure B.2 we present results for the system $\text{CH}_4 + \text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}$ in a similar way. For both systems we observe a good quantitative performance by the model, as it was previously depicted for the methane + n-triacontane system.

APPENDIX C: ADDITIONAL MODELING RESULTS FOR THE SYSTEM METHANE + N-TRIACONTANE

To increase our understanding of the model performance for the system $\text{CH}_4 + \text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$, we present here phase equilibrium diagrams at constant pressure. Figure 8, in the main body of this article, presents a set of horizontal lines corresponding to the isobars at 831 bar, 1400 bar and 1731 bar. At 1400 bar we observe an intersection on the critical line and another one, at higher temperature, on the melting curve. We also see such key points in Figure C.2 which shows the isobar at 1400 bar. This isobar has, according to the model, a liquid-vapour region of small size that extends from a SLV point to a critical point, a solid-liquid region between the SLV point and the pure n-triacontane melting point at about 372 K, and a solid-vapour region from the SLV point towards lower temperatures up to the minimum temperature of applicability of the present model (T_p). At 1400 bar we are far above the triple point pressure and also above the experimental second critical end point pressure ($1285.5 \pm 5 \text{ bar}$)¹, thus, experimentally, only a single solid-fluid region should appear. Instead of that, the model predicts the existence of both, a solid-fluid region and a vapor-liquid region of small size because the second critical end point pressure is over predicted by the model ($\approx 1540 \text{ bar} > 1400 \text{ bar}$), as it was previously discussed.

In Figure 8 of the main text, the horizontal line at 831 bar intersects the melting curve of pure n-triacontane. There is also an intersection point with the critical line that happens at high temperature beyond the scale of Figure 8. Figure C.1 shows the corresponding isobaric cut. In this case, the binary critical temperature is much higher than the pure n-triacontane melting temperature. The value of the calculated critical temperature should not be considered an artefact of the model in view of the good agreement between the model and the experimental data that Figure C.1 shows. In Figure C.2 the behaviour is opposite to that of Figure C.1, in the sense that the critical temperature is less than the heavy component melting temperature for Figure C.2. Eventually these two temperature values become equal. This happens at the intersection point between the critical line and the melting line in Figure 8, at about 1200 bar and 367 K.

At 1731 bar, the pressure is higher than that of the 2nd CEP (i.e., higher than about $P = 1540$ bar, i.e., the 2nd CEP pressure for the model). Thus, according to Figure 8, there is only one key point, i.e., a pure n-triacontane melting point. Figure C.3 presents the isobaric cut at 1731 bar. Now we just see a solid-liquid region that originates at the pure heavy component melting point and extends toward lower temperatures.

Overall, the Figures C.1, C.2 and C.3 confirm an acceptable performance by the SF model. This could have been anticipated by drawing constant pressure horizontal lines on the chart of Figure 3. We stress that the model properly matches the pure heavy component solid-liquid equilibrium limit as depicted in the isobaric cuts of Figures C.1, C.2 and C.3

Table 1. Properties and constants of pure n-triacontane

Compound	T_{tp} / K^{**}	P_{tp} / bar^{***}	C_I / bar^*	$C_{II} / (bar/K)^*$	$C_{III} / (bar/K^2)^*$	$v_2^S / (m^3/Kmol)^*$
n-C ₃₀ H ₆₂	338.65	2.33211 10 ⁻⁹	-2.87143 10 ⁻¹	-32.08914	1.05340 10 ⁻¹	0.6300

** From DIPPR database ¹⁹. *** P_{tp} = PR-EOS pure compound vapour-liquid equilibrium pressure at the triple point temperature T_{tp} (this work). * Parameter values obtained in this work.

Table 2. Binary interaction parameters for the PR-EOS (this work)

System	k_{ij}	l_{ij}	AAD %	Experimental data reference
CH ₄ (1) + n-C ₃₀ H ₆₂ (2)	0.0611	0.0206	5.7	¹

Table 3. Pure compound properties from DIPPR database ¹⁹

Compound	T_{crit} / K	P_{crit} / Bar	ω
CH ₄	190.564	45.99	0.0115478
n-C ₃₀ H ₆₂	844	8.0	1.3072

T_{crit} = Critical Temperature. P_{crit} = Critical Pressure. ω = acentric factor.

Table B.1. Properties and constants of pure n-eicosane and n-tetracosane.

Compound	T_{tp} / K^{**}	P_{tp} / bar^{***}	C_I / bar^*	$C_{II} / (bar/K)^*$	$C_{III} / (bar/K^2)^*$	$v_2^S / (m^3/Kmol)^*$
n-C ₂₀ H ₄₂	309.58	2.10471 10 ⁻⁷	-11.13842	-189.40223	3.62841 10 ⁻¹	0.3933
n-C ₂₄ H ₅₀	323.75	3.20150 10 ⁻⁸	-8.37418 10 ⁻²	2.77808 10 ⁻¹	6.70808 10 ⁻²	0.4932

** From DIPPR database ¹⁹. *** P_{tp} = PR-EOS pure compound vapour-liquid equilibrium pressure at the triple point temperature T_{tp} (this work). * Parameter values obtained in this work.

Table B.2. Binary interaction parameters for the PR-EOS (this work)

System	k_{ij}	l_{ij}	AAD %	Experimental data reference
CH ₄ (1) + n-C ₂₀ H ₄₂ (2)	0.0631	0.0134	8.1	²
CH ₄ (1) + n-C ₂₄ H ₅₀ (2)	0.0596	0.0132	6.2	³

Table B.3. Pure compound properties from DIPPR database ¹⁹

Compound	T_{crit} / K	P_{crit} / Bar	ω
n-C ₂₀ H ₄₂	768	11.6	0.9069
n-C ₂₄ H ₅₀	804	9.8	1.0710

T_{crit} = Critical Temperature. P_{crit} = Critical Pressure. ω = acentric factor.

Figure 1. Solid-liquid equilibrium (Melting) pressure as a function of temperature for pure n-eicosane, pure n-tetracosane and pure n-triacontane. Lines: eq 9 with parameters from Table B.1 for n-eicosane (—) and n-tetracosane (dot-dash), and from Table 1 for n-triacontane (dot-dot-dash). Markers: experimental data for pure n-eicosane (circles), n-tetracosane (triangles) and n-triacontane(☆) from refs ², ³ and ¹ respectively.

Figure 2. Bubble pressure as a function of temperature (isopleths) for the system methane (CH_4) + n -triacontane ($n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$) at varying $n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ mole fraction. Exception: The $x_{n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.02$ curve corresponds to a dew point isopleth. Markers: raw experimental data from ref ¹. Lines: PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3. The labels shown on the chart correspond to the values for the $n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ mole fraction.

Figure 3. Solid-fluid equilibrium for the system methane (CH_4) + n-triacontane ($\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$). Markers: raw isoplethic experimental data from ref ¹: ☆ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.020$, ▲ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.025$, ○ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.030$, + $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.050$, × $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.103$, * $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.202$, ∇ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.307$, ◇ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.402$, ● $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.5$, ⊠ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.645$, △ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.85$, ★ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 1$. This chart also includes SLV experimental equilibrium data (●). Lines: Calculated SF equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from tables 1 to 3. Labels indicating the $\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ fluid phase mole fraction values for the calculated isopleths are shown on the chart. Vertical dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure $\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ ¹⁹ (Table 1). Figure 4 shows more clearly the isopleths with lowest n-triacontane concentration.

Figure 4. Zoom of the higher methane concentration portion of Figure 3. Solid-fluid equilibrium for the system methane (CH_4) + n-triacontane ($\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$). Markers: raw isoplethic experimental data from ref ¹: ☆ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.020$, ▲ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.025$, ○ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.030$, + $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.050$, × $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.103$, * $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.202$, ▽ $x_{\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}} = 0.307$. Lines: Calculated SF equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Labels indicating the n- $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ fluid phase mole fraction values for the calculated isopleths are shown on the chart. Vertical dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure n- $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ ¹⁹ (Table 1).

Figure 5. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH₄) + n-triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂) at 340.34 K. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data ¹. Full black triangles: experimental liquid-vapour equilibrium data ¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Dashed lines: Calculated vapor-liquid equilibrium using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3. Circles: Calculated solid-liquid-vapour equilibrium (this work).

Figure 6. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH_4) + n-triacontane ($\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$) at 343.15 K. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data ¹. Full black triangles: experimental liquid-vapor equilibrium data ¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Dashed lines: Calculated vapor-liquid equilibrium using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3.

Figure 7. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH₄) + n-triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂) at 353.15 K. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data ¹. Full black triangles: experimental liquid-vapor equilibrium data ¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Dashed lines: Calculated vapor-liquid equilibrium using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3.

Figure 8. Some calculated univariant lines for the system methane (CH_4) + n-triacontane ($\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$). The melting curve for pure $\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ was calculated using eq 9 with parameters from Table 1. The vapour pressure curve for pure $\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ was calculated using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Table 3. The binary vapor-liquid critical locus was calculated using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3. Circles: Experimental solid-liquid-vapour equilibrium data from ref¹. Vertical dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure $\text{n-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ ¹⁹ (Table 1). This chart also presents a set of horizontal lines corresponding to the isobars of 831 bar, 1400 bar and 1731 bar; and a set of vertical lines corresponding to the isotherms of 340.34 K, 343.15 K and 353.15 K.

Figure B.1. Solid-fluid equilibrium for the system methane (CH_4) + n-eicosane ($\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}$). Markers: raw isoplethic experimental data from ref²: $+$ $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.177$, \times $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.252$, $*$ $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.363$, squares: $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.488$, \diamond $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.616$, \bullet $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 0.74$, \star $x_{\text{n-C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}} = 1$. This chart also includes SLV experimental equilibrium data (\bullet). Lines: Calculated SF equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables B.1, B.2 and B.3. Labels indicating the n- $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}$ fluid phase mole fraction values for the calculated isopleths are shown on the chart. Vertical dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure n- $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}$ ¹⁹ (Table B.1).

Figure B.2. Solid-fluid equilibrium for the system methane (CH_4) + n-tetracosane ($\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}$). Markers: raw isoplethic experimental data from ref³: \blacktriangle $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.010$, \bigcirc $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.052$, $+$ $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.164$, \times $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.256$, $*$ $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.359$, ∇ $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.451$, \diamond $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.555$, squares: $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 0.752$, \star $x_{\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}} = 1$. This chart also includes SLV experimental equilibrium data (\bullet). Lines: Calculated SF equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables B.1, B.2 and B.3. Labels indicating the $\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}$ fluid phase mole fraction values for the calculated isopleths are shown on the chart. Vertical dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure $\text{n-C}_{24}\text{H}_{50}$ ¹⁹ (Table B.1).

Figure C.1. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH_4) + n-triacontane ($n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$) at 831 bar. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data¹. Full black triangles: experimental liquid-vapor equilibrium data¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Dashed curves: Calculated vapor-liquid equilibrium using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3. Horizontal dashed line: Experimental triple point temperature (T_{tp}) of pure $n\text{-C}_{30}\text{H}_{62}$ ¹⁹ (Table 1).

Figure C.2. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH₄) + n-triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂) at 1400 bar. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data ¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Dashed curves: Calculated vapor-liquid equilibrium using the PR-EOS⁵ with parameters from Tables 2 and 3. Circles: Calculated solid-liquid-vapour equilibrium (this work). T_{tp}: experimental triple point temperature of pure n-C₃₀H₆₂ ¹⁹ (Table 1).

Figure C.3. Phase behaviour for the system methane (CH₄) + n-triacontane (n-C₃₀H₆₂) at 1731 bar. Empty triangles: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data ¹. Lines: — Calculated solid-fluid equilibrium using the model from this work, with parameters from Tables 1 to 3. Horizontal dashed line: experimental triple point temperature (**T_{tp}**) of pure n-C₃₀H₆₂ ¹⁹ (Table 1).

NOMENCLATURE

1 = light compound

1st CEP = first critical end point

2 = heavy compound

2nd CEP = second critical end point

C_I, C_{II}, C_{III} = constants that characterize the melting curve ($P_2^{sat,SL}$) of pure compound 2 (i.e., of the heavy component)

E = equilibrium

\hat{f}_i = fugacity of component "i" in a fluid mixture

f_2^S = fugacity of component 2 (i.e., of the heavy component) as a pure solid

$f_2^{sat,SL}$ = melting saturation fugacity of the heavy component

$f_2^{sat,SV}$ = sublimation saturation fugacity of the heavy component

L = liquid phase

LV = liquid-vapor

P = absolute pressure

P_{tp} = pure heavy compound triple point absolute pressure

$P_2^{sat,SL}$ = melting saturation pressure of the heavy component

$P_2^{sat,SV}$ = sublimation saturation pressure of the heavy component

R = universal gas constant

S = solid phase

SF = solid-fluid

SFE = solid-fluid equilibrium

SFF = solid-fluid-fluid

SL = solid-liquid

SLE = solid-liquid equilibrium

SLV = solid-liquid-vapor

SV = solid-vapor

T = absolute temperature

T_{tp} = pure heavy compound triple point absolute temperature

ν = molar volume

ν_o = molar volume of pure saturated liquid at solid-liquid equilibrium conditions

ν_2^S = molar volume of the pure solid

ν_y = molar volume of the fluid phase at SFE conditions

V = vapor phase

y_2 = mole fraction of component 2 (i.e., of the heavy component) in the fluid phase

z_2 = mole fraction of component 2 (i.e., of the heavy component)

$\phi_2^{sat,SL}$ = melting saturation fugacity coefficient of the pure heavy component

$\phi_2^{sat,SV}$ = sublimation saturation fugacity coefficient of the pure heavy component

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